

ON MONOTONIC MODELS FOR CLINICAL EVENT PREDICTIONS (WORKING PAPER, VERSION JUNE 2, 2026)

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ABSTRACT. Predictors of clinical event rates frequently employ a monotonic model, such as exponential, logistic or linear, fitted on cohort datasets. Baseline measurements are used as independent variables and the rate of events observed later are the dependent variable. Such models assume a monotonic relationship between the dependent and each of the independent variables.

However, in observational studies, this relationship is often ‘U-shaped’ for parameters such as concentrations of blood constituents, arterial pressure or body mass index. Most of these have an optimal physiologic range, outside of which pathological phenomena occur.

To provide an example, we calculated the univariate relationship between blood cholesterol and systolic blood pressure with the SCORE2 predictions, which is monotonic when all other parameters are kept constant. We compared it with the published results of large cohort studies, where this relationship is U-shaped. We found a contrasting tendency between predicted and measured event rates for low non-HDL cholesterol or low systolic blood pressure.

Similar differences might characterise other applications of monotonic regression for clinical event prediction. Parameter adjustments cannot reduce such differences as the model function will remain monotonic irrespective of its parameters.

As a possible approach to this issue, we suggest the development of a “direct predictor” where a cohort dataset is used to select the subset of data with parameter configurations similar to the case of interest and the event rate observed in the subset is taken as prediction for the case.

In conclusion, we stress the importance of the parameter range and specific population subgroup specification for the application of existing monotonic prediction models. More complex functions, or completely different methods, may be needed in order to improve clinical event risk predictions.

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1. INTRODUCTION

We aim to describe and illustrate the limits of modelling relationships, that are not monotonic, using a monotonic function.

Some predictive algorithms, such as SCORE [3], SCORE2 [12] or the Framingham Risk Score [4], use monotonic models that are fitted on parameter and clinical event data.

1.1. The ‘U-shape’. Most physiologic parameters are associated with an increased rate of unfavorable clinical events, including death, both at lower and at higher values outside an optimal (normal) range. In other words, their univariate relationship with the rate appears ‘U-shaped’ in graphics. Examples are: the heart rate, blood pressure, blood concentrations of hemoglobin, cholesterol or glucose, the body mass index etc.

More complex relationship occur in some cases, but this ‘U-shape’ is typical.

There are other measurable variables that do not exhibit an ‘U-shape’ but a monotonic relationship, such as various disease markers that are normally absent.

1.2. Mathematical properties. Predictors such as the Framingham Score, SCORE or SCORE2, include the clinical variables in the form of an expression like:

$$(1) \quad c^{e^{-\beta X}}$$

where:

$$(2) \quad \beta X = \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots \beta_n x_n$$

where x_i , are the clinical measurable variables. The β_i coefficients are constants (the same for all cases) that are established during the fitting process. c is also a constant resulting from fitting.

Monotonicity, which is a feature of single-variable functions, results from the fact that, when we choose any variable x_i , and keep the other constant, the resulting function in x_i is a linear function which is monotonous with respect to x_i , that is it always either increasing or decreasing with x_i (depending on the sign of β_i). Exponentiation and other transformations found in the formulas do not change the monotonicity, only possibly its direction (increasing or decreasing).

The curves in the bottom graphics in figures 1 and 2 represent such series, computed for SCORE2, where the variable choosen, x_i , represents colesterol and, respectively, systolic blood pressure.

In order to avoid a monotonic relationship, a straightforward approach would be for the respective variable to also appear squared as a supplementary $\beta_{n+1} x_{n+1}$ term in the formula.

2. METHODS

We computed series of SCORE2 risk estimates. In each series, we kept all variables constant except for one that changed along its range.

SCORE2 was computed using the procedure from the RiskScorescvd R package [11], modified to use mg/dL instead of mmol/L. We verified the accuracy of the algorithm

FIGURE 1. Top: A and B, reproduced from part of figure 2 from [1]. Bottom: graphics of hazard ratios of total cholesterol predicted with SCORE2. Both graphics represent the same simulated data, with different levels chosen as reference. Red represents women, blue represents men, each curve corresponds to one age (40, 50, 60, 70). The minimal SCORE2 risk non-HDL cholesterol level, that is 0mg/dL, was taken as reference in the left graphic, the minimal risk level associated to total cholesterol, observed in the general population, of 200mg/dL, in the right graphic.

FIGURE 2. Top: reproduced from part of figure 2 from [10]. Bottom: graphics of hazard ratio for systolic blood pressure, predicted with SCORE2. Both graphics represent the same simulated data, with different levels chosen as reference. Red represents women, blue represents men, each line corresponds to a one-year age group (40, 50, 60, 70). In the SCORE2 model the minimal risk corresponds to a systolic blood pressure of 0mmHg, which was taken as reference in the left graphic. The experimental optimal systolic blood pressure of 110mmHg, in the general population, was taken as reference in the right graphic.

by checking a few examples with the European Society of Cardiology HeartScore online calculator.

In the cholesterol series we kept HDL cholesterol at 50mg/dL, and changed total cholesterol from 50mg/dL to 500mg/dL; systolic blood pressure was kept at 130mmHg,

all where non-smoker and non-diabetic and separate series were obtained for ages 40, 50, 60 and 70 years old and for each gender; the regional risk was always “High”.

In the blood pressure series we kept the HDL cholesterol at 50mg/dL, the total cholesterol at 200mg/dL and all other parameters as for the cholesterol series. Systolic blood pressure was varied from 0 to 200mmHg.

3. RESULTS

Calculation results are displayed in the bottom two graphs of each of figures 1, for cholesterol, and 2 for systolic blood pressure. The top four graphs in each figure are taken from large population studies, [1] and [10].

The monotonic relationships between event rates and each of the variables (total/non-HDL cholesterol and systolic blood pressure) can be observed.

The minimal calculated SCORE2 risk in all series occur for a non-HDL cholesterol of 0mg/dL and for a systolic blood pressure of 0mmHg respectively, as expected for a monotonic model.

4. DISCUSSION

We compared predictions by the SCORE2 formula [12, 11] with observational results in large cohorts. For lower values of cholesterol and systolic blood pressure, we found that the increase in mortality, cardiovascular mortality and, implicitly, major cardiovascular events, that is well known from observational studies [10, 15, 6, 8, 7, 1, 9] is not reproduced by the SCORE2 function, that indicate a decreased event rate for these lower values.

While we did a few calculations to illustrate the difference, this was to be expected from the fact that SCORE2 is a monotonic function with respect to cholesterol and systolic blood pressure.

A possible similar phenomenon needs to be verified for any prediction model based on a monotonic function, when one or more independent (explanatory) variables has a univariate U-shaped relationship with the dependent variable.

The fact that such a predictor is inadequate for some range of the independent variable does not imply that they are not useful on some specified range. In our example, SCORE2 is adequate on levels of total cholesterol above 200mg/dL and systolic blood pressure above 100mmHg.

4.1. Implications for practice. Such limits of application of predictors are usually carefully described in the papers where they are introduced [3, 12, 4, 2], and also enforced by some automated calculators (such as HeartScore). Further application limits refer to the specific groups of patients to which the guidelines based on these predictors apply [5, 13],

However, the practice of taking the limits into account may not always be adopted by users, other calculators and various educational materials in a uniform and effective manner, resulting in eventual mispredictions and misconceptions. For example, normality and/or desirability ranges for cholesterol in a laboratory results bulletin, shown in figure 3, which do not have a lower bound. Such notices are addressed to the general

population. They contrast to the optimal ranges for cholesterol as observed in large general population studies [1, 15] and partially shown in figures 1 and 2.

Many similar examples can be found online and in practice. While introducing complex subcategories and conditions may be impractical in such notices, perhaps more efforts would be justified to avoid misleading patients. In our opinion, “normal” limits for cholesterol in the general population, that take into account general mortality and morbidity, could be revised, using direct observational results like [1, 15] rather than extrapolations of monotonic model functions.

4.2. Fitting limitations. An important question is whether, and how, a monotonic model, that fails to predict for some ranges of its arguments, appear to perform well overall.

The answer depends on the structure of the dataset from which the β and c coefficients are established by fitting. It may be a complex dataset in multivariate models. An apparently good fit can be observed if there are large differences in the relative weight of the β coefficients for each variable and/or in the relative prevalence of cases in the discordant range—low values of cholesterol and arterial pressure in our case.

For SCORE2, we did not directly analyse this issue which requires a complete cohort dataset. However, speculatively, age is one of the most powerful general predictors of mortality, especially in older people. The age/mortality relation is also ‘U-shaped’, infants having a higher mortality than young people, that decreases with age. SCORE2 deals only with adults, where the age/mortality relation is monotonic, mortality exponentially increases with age, strongly on older population groups.

On the background of a strong, truly monotonic, contribution of age to the SCORE2 prediction, a relatively small number of cases with low cholesterol and/or low blood pressure may not influence the fitting indicators much.

4.3. Approaches for better models. SCORE2 underestimates cardiovascular event risk in some population groups [14]. Our results may provide a further possible explanation why this observed underestimation may occur in some cases. We think the general observation from [14], that more variables should be employed for cardiovascular event risk prediction, is important.

By recalibrating the β indices it is possible to obtain any concordance with observed event rates in the overall population, because there are many parameters that can be changed to obtain a fit of a single number. However, it is not necessarily possible to obtain a good fit simultaneously in all subgroups. In particular, in the case of SCORE2, one cannot obtain a good fit simultaneously in high cholesterol and in low cholesterol subgroups.

For that purpose, a different class of model functions, that includes an U-shaped model for some variables, needs to be used. The simplest approach would be to introduce squared values of these variables in the model, that would provide a U-shaped component.

A good example of a predictive score that takes into account both abnormal ends of the cholesterol range is described by Lee et al. in reference [9]. Risk points are added for both too low or too high cholesterol.

Colesterol total		154	mg/dL	Nivel optim: <200 mg/dl Nivel de atentie: 200-240 mg/dl Nivel de risc: >240 mg/dl
<i>Ser, metoda spectrofotometrica, Alinity Abbott</i>				
HDL - Colesterol				
<i>Ser, metoda spectrofotometrica, Alinity Abbott</i>				
HDL Colesterol	38		mg/dL	Risc scazut : > 60 mg/dL Risc moderat : 40 -59 mg/dL Risc crescut : < 40 mg/dL;
LDL-Colesterol				
<i>Ser, metoda spectrofotometrica / calcul, Alinity Abbott</i>				
LDL-Colesterol	79.2		mg/dL	Nivel optim: <100 mg/dL Risc scazut: 100 - 129 mg/dL Risc moderat: 130 - 159 mg/dL Risc crescut: 160 - 189 mg/dL Risc foarte crescut: >=190 mg/dL

FIGURE 3. Fragment from a laboratory bulletin (in Romanian). The “optimal” range of total cholesterol recommended is under 200mg/dL, without a lower limit. A value of 155 mg/dL is not labeled as abnormal. In [15], figure 2, such a value is associated with 40% higher general mortality in males than the 210-240mg/dL, that has the lowest mortality. For LDL-C, the recommended ‘range’ is below 100mg/dL, without a lower limit. The value of 79 mg/dL is not labeled as abnormal. In [1], figure 2, partly reproduced as figure 1 in this paper, this value is also associated with increased mortality in the general population. Similar classifications of ‘normality’ are frequently found across the world.

Models could also be improved by fitting with a more diverse range of literature data. For example, a general model of the population could be developed, that makes predictions for all the marginal (single variable) population results that are present in literature, and allows validation with each of them, rather than with their general average.

Another approach, when large cohort datasets are available, and when not too many variables are included, could be a **direct predictor**: given a patient profile, identify all the cases in the dataset that have variable values close to the patient’s and take the event rate in that dataset as prediction. This method still makes the assumption that event rate in the last decade(s) and in the population in which the dataset was collected will be the same in the patient’s population at current time, but avoid some other assumptions such as monotonicity.

The direct predictor would also have the advantage that, when only a limited set of the predictive variables are available, a prediction can still be made, using marginal probability distributions.

It has the disadvantage that, when there are many predictive variables, the number of cases in the dataset that are similar to the case of interest may be too small for a risk estimation. Also, the use of a direct predictor requires access to a computer that contains the whole database and performs large scale computations for each prediction. It cannot be developed into a convenient colored nomogram or a score calculation by adding points.

4.4. Limitations. The SCORE2 variable for cholesterol is in fact the ‘non-HDL’ cholesterol, the difference between total cholesterol and HDL. The available data in [15, 1] were for total and LDL cholesterol. LDL is a fraction of ‘non-HDL’. Also, the predicted event in SCORE2 is cardiovascular mortality combined with stroke or myocardial infarction, while in [1] it is only cardiovascular mortality or all-cause mortality. In [15] and [10] it is all-cause mortality.

Thus, our comparisons are not strictly consistent. However, the totally opposite hazard ratio trends and the physiologically impossible minimal event rate at zero blood pressure and zero non-HDL cholesterol implied by the monotonic model show that there is a significant mismatch between model and observational data.

4.5. Conclusions. Predictive models based on monotonic functions underestimate event rates in some patient groups, when some of the independent variables have an U-shaped relationship with the dependent one. Simple recalibrations can not improve prediction in these groups and different predictors are needed.

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